

AI's Applicability to the Legal Profession

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence's ('AI') piecemeal introduction to the law is integral to maintaining the integrity of the legal profession. This is on account of AI's hallucinatory abilities to generate content and subsequent risks this poses in ensuring accurate legal knowledge is conveyed to the general public. The likelihood of spreading legal misinformation is further exacerbated due to systemic American biases present in current language learning models ('LLMs') – an issue encountered during my study of AI-Enabled Politics and International Relations ('ARTX3500'). It is therefore necessary that LLMs are subject to ongoing scrutiny and regulation by bodies responsible for their administration, with the impetus of eradicating inherent bias altogether. This case study will discuss insights garnered during the study of ARTX3500 concerning the use of AI in educational and personal contexts from a legal standpoint. Accrued insights assert that AI proves useful in performing administrative tasks – namely, to summarise information and plan written submissions – and thus, can be integrated into the legal profession. Use of LLMs to complete clerical processes illustrate that indeed, AI can be utilised in a manner that maintains the importance of critical thinking to the legal profession.

Introduction

The use of AI across the Australian tertiary education landscape is varied, depending heavily on one's area of study or the discretion of individual institutions. Prior to my enrolment in ARTX3500, I considered AI to be largely irrelevant to the study of law due to the traditionalist, highly prescriptive values inherent to the discipline. These perceptions were informed by prevailing attitudes held by the Australian judicial system, which has opined that AI and LLMs, on account of their 'hallucinatory' abilities, (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024), are to be regarded with scepticism. This misconception continues to pervade humanities-based areas of study, many of which are reluctant to accept AI's rising influence in modern society.

As an undergraduate student studying Law and International Relations, I initially assumed my conservative beliefs concerning the legal realm's scepticism of AI would remain unchanged; that indeed, AI held little relevance to a field reluctant to utilise modern technology in its undertakings. On the contrary, this assumption was challenged throughout the semester. My exposure to various applications of AI in legal contexts demonstrated their value and utility, significantly contradicting

my earlier views concerning the law's reluctance to embrace new technologies. Changes to my perspectives were further reinforced by recent legal developments, including the issuing of guidance concerning the use of AI in legal practice by the Chief Justice of New South Wales in 2024. On account of these developments, concomitant to my engagement with the course content, I have come to recognise AI's increasing value to the legal profession.

Methodology and Outline of Case Study

Defined as a research method utilising personal knowledge to describe and interpret beliefs and experiences (Clarke, 2015), autoethnography has been crucial in clarifying my varied viewpoints on AI over the course of the university semester. Yin's Design Principles and structural adherence to a case study design focusing on systematic data collection and analysis will be employed to exemplify my varied viewpoints taken towards AI and LLM use throughout the university semester.

This case study will be organised into a series of chronological reflections corresponding to key stages of studying ARTX3500. It begins with a discussion concerning my initial expectations on AI usage and the course itself, followed by an examination of key learning experiences and challenges during the semester. Particular emphasis will be placed upon how my understanding of AI has evolved in personal and professional contexts, especially with regard to the use of LLMs in legal practice. The study concludes by noting recommendations for integration of AI in the legal profession based on knowledge accrued in ARTX3500.

1. Initial impressions of AI

My initial perceptions of AI were largely shaped by my academic background in law and politics at the tertiary level. Prior to enrolling in ARTX3500, I believed AI was largely incompatible with the legal profession, an industry I perceived to be underpinned by elitism and traditionalist practices. This perspective rings true, aligning with existing commentary on the Australian judicial system's risk-averse, piecemeal approach to using AI in legal practice, as noted by Mimi Zou, Professor at UNSW Law & Justice (Ea, 2024).

Overall, my approach to AI was dichotomous: I harboured apprehensions towards such new technologies due to AI's potential risks and unfamiliarity. And yet, I recognised the law's need to adapt to societal technological advancements, and wanted to explore how AI may be applied within legal contexts. Furthermore, I was particularly interested to learn how developing a working knowledge of AI would provide me with transferable skills to be utilised in the legal profession. I

note that prior to enrolling in ARTX3500, my engagement with AI was limited to informal and recreational use. This new exploration of AI within an academic context contradicted my prior use of LLMs, given that I was now learning how to employ AI usage within academic and professional contexts.

Preliminary assumptions I held about AI were quickly challenged. Contrary to my aforementioned beliefs, I came to recognise that AI possessed utility in a range of contexts. This realisation occurred in my first ARTX3500 class, during which I was introduced to the concept of the ‘system prompt.’ Defined by OpenAI (OpenAI ChatGPT, 2025) as an instruction that sets the AI’s behaviour, tone, and scope of knowledge at the outset of a session, the system prompt was integral in disproving myths – specifically, the notion that AI was to be used as a search engine – held prior to beginning ARTX3500. To understand that system prompts could be used to condense information based on user input was highly insightful. This realisation in turn resonated with concepts discussed within International Relations, where theoretical lenses are employed to examine the global distribution of power.

However, as I continued to utilise system prompts throughout the semester, I observed marked variability in the ability of AI to synthesise information. This was especially evident in instances where the system prompt lacked precision or context, generating a poor output.

Furthermore, class discussions with my peer group informed me that legal questions posed without hyperspecific system prompts would be answered by the AI model from an American perspective. I tested the latter hypothesis and prompted ChatGPT-4o to explain the significance of corporations law within the Australian context. The prompts used and the corresponding outputs (summarised for brevity) are as follows:

Prompt: *Please explain the importance of corporations law within the Australian context.*

Output: *Corporations law is critically important within the Australian context because it forms the legal framework that governs the creation, operation, regulation, and dissolution of companies. Its significance can be understood through several key dimensions:*

1. *Facilitating Economic Activity*
2. *Promoting Investor Confidence*
3. *Ensuring Corporate Accountability...*

Prompt: Please explain the significance of corporations law.

Output: Corporations law is significant because it:

- Enables business formation and continuity
- Protects economic participants
- Ensures corporate accountability
- Supports national and global economic systems.

Without it, companies would lack structure, markets would lose credibility, and economic growth would be unstable and unregulated (OpenAI ChatGPT, 2024).

I noted that without specifying the Australian legal context, outputs by the LLM were vague, though did not hold particular American bias. This experiment informed me of the need to be detailed and context-specific when utilising AI in educational and professional legal settings.

2. Turning Points in the Course

As noted previously, my worldview toward AI was challenged significantly during the early stages of ARTX3500. This was primarily due to the academic convenor's directive that students engage with AI in both academic and personal contexts on a daily basis. This requirement was strikingly unfamiliar, given the prohibitions on AI use in my professional workplace and the broader legal discipline, where AI use remains highly regulated. Under the guidance of my academic convenor, I utilised AI in my educational and personal settings, thereby broadening my understanding of AI's applicability in a variety of social contexts. The following sections will discuss my use of AI in educational and personal contexts, making reference to my changing views on AI as the course progressed.

Educational Use of AI

Prior to beginning ARTX3500, I believed that AI had limited value within the legal discipline – a belief reinforced by the strict guidelines enforced at Macquarie University Law School ('MULS'). These policies mirrored the Chief Justice of New South Wales' reluctance to integrate AI use in legal study and processes (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024). In fact, much of the

academic staff at MULS emphasised the facetious nature of AI, noting that its ability to generate – ‘hallucinate,’ as asserted by the NSW Chief Justice – potentially false information impeded one’s ability to exercise independent critical thinking.

Despite this, my engagement with ARTX3500 informed me of AI’s ability to be utilised in a manner that accommodated my – and the legal profession’s – reservations. Keeping these accommodations in mind, I began using AI for permissible administrative tasks such as grammatical checking, summarising information and drafting written submissions – functions permitted pursuant to *Practice Note SC Gen 23 – Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence* (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024). I enjoyed using AI within this context due to its efficiency and minimally invasive nature (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024), allowing me to focus primarily on substantive aspects of legal writing.

I note that while I was cognisant of AI’s ability to generate entire written submissions, I consciously refrained from employing AI in this manner. As echoed in passing statements made by staff at MULS, using AI to do so did not assist in consolidating my knowledge or bettering my writing skills. Furthermore, LLMs would often rely on sources lacking academic credibility when generating written content, many of which were not fact-checked or peer-reviewed. For instance, when performing research for topics related to my International Relations Arts major, I was redirected to sources such as Quora – a user-generated platform which was neither peer-reviewed or verified. Due to these limitations, I vehemently disliked using AI models to generate written pieces of work and instead used LLMs in a manner which supported, rather than replaced, my intellectual engagement.

Personal Use of AI

The challenge to incorporate AI use on a daily basis prompted me to attempt incorporating AI in my personal life. Drawing upon my experience using LLMs for planning and scheduling purposes, I experimented with AI by exploring its potential as a digital styling assistant. This was done through using AI as a styling assistant wherein I prompted the LLM Claude 3.5 Sonnet to generate outfit ideas for various contexts. While using AI in this regard, I provided the LLM with variables such as the weather forecast, subcultures I was interested in, colours I liked to wear and specific information regarding my appearance. One such example is included below to illustrate the customisability and interactivity of this process:

System Prompt: *You are a styling assistant for a tertiary-level undergraduate student. Your job is to devise outfits your client would like, with the impetus of alleviating her demanding workload.*

Prompt: *Hello Claude, I require assistance creating an outfit for the day. It is currently 18 degrees Celsius in Sydney, Australia, where I am located. I gravitate towards wearing darker hues – namely grey and black, occasionally red – and am inspired by the following subcultures: alternative e-girl, mall goth, kogal Gyaruru and Harajuku style. Appearance-wise, I have red highlights and usually wear makeup inspired by classic Gyaruru/ Chinese makeup styles inspired by the online media platform XiaoHongShu.*

Taking into account the above information, please create an outfit for me. Thank you.

The output received upon submitting the above were highly appreciated, given their accuracy to the detail I included in my prompt. While I believed the information provided was surface-level, the LLM produced an outfit taking into account all aspects of my request. A summarised version of Claude 3.5 Sonnet's response to the above prompts is as follows:

Output: *Based on your style preferences and the 18°C Sydney weather, here's a perfect outfit that blends your favorite subcultures:*

Top Layer:

- *Black oversized band tee or graphic tee with distressed details*
- *Layered under a cropped grey zip-up hoodie or black mesh long-sleeve top for that e-girl layering effect*

Bottom:

- *High-waisted black pleated mini skirt (kogal-inspired) or black wide-leg pants with chain details*
- *Black or grey striped thigh-high socks or fishnet stockings*

Outerwear:

- *Black denim jacket with patches or pins, or a grey oversized cardigan for warmth while maintaining the aesthetic*

Footwear:

- *Black platform boots (Doc Martens style) or chunky black sneakers*
- *Alternatively, Mary Jane platforms in black for a more Harajuku touch*

This outfit works perfectly for 18°C weather with comfortable layering options, while seamlessly blending the edgy alternative e-girl elements with the cute kogal pleated skirt aesthetic and Harajuku accessory styling. The darker palette matches your preferences while the textures and layering keep it interesting and true to your inspiration sources (OpenAI, 2024).

Utilising AI in this personal capacity provided insight concerning AI's relevance to all aspects of daily life. In this context, AI usage allowed me to conserve my cognitive resources for more onerous tasks of more importance such as university coursework and professional responsibilities. By delegating administrative tasks to the LLM, I was able to work effectively on tasks that required exercising critical thinking. In this instance, the LLM model fulfilled its system prompt instructions, completing minor, yet time-consuming tasks, whilst simultaneously reducing my overall workload.

I have since taken insights from this exercise and continue to integrate AI use in everyday life by employing LLMs to carry out clerical procedures. Most recently, I have been using ChatGPT-4o to generate tailored study timetables in preparation for my university examination period – a task which, when completed by myself, has previously taken between 20 minutes to an hour due to the time spent accommodating for my occupational and extracurricular activities. This contrasts to using LLMs, which takes less than 15 minutes to complete upon being provided prompts concerning the details of my work and extracurricular activities. Use of these technologies for this clerical purpose saves time while also facilitating an efficient approach to academic preparation.

3. Revised Perspectives on AI

By the conclusion of ARTX3500, I was of the opinion that AI was simultaneously relevant to the legal profession and my personal life – a stark contrast to my prior scepticism on AI integration in these contexts. While my perspectives have shifted significantly, this does not equate to idolatry acceptance; rather, AI usage requires ongoing scrutinisation, monitoring and regulation. The status of LLMs as a recent technological development possesses tangible risks to the legal profession, given AI's 'hallucinatory' abilities and ability to fabricate information (Ea, 2024).

Care must therefore be exercised to utilise AI alongside one's critical thinking skills as noted in *Practice Note SC Gen 23 – Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence* (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024), which delegates AI to administrative tasks when completing legal processes. As outlined in the latter document, AI should be used in legal settings for the sole purposes of administrative and support functions. My practical and academic applications of AI during ARTX3500 reaffirmed this belief, and I have experienced firsthand the need to proscribe AI usage within the legal context due to the paramount importance of accurate legal knowledge – a concept which AI has yet to grasp.

I note that my experience working in the legal profession has highlighted the implications unregulated AI use has on the Australian judicial system. For instance, I have been privy to a case wherein a self-represented litigant employed LLM usage to draft their Court submissions – an act prohibited under Practice Notes of various judicial jurisdictions (Supreme Court of New South Wales, 2024). In this instance, the litigant invoked amendments from the United States Bill of Rights and various human rights principles – neither of which were applicable, given that the matter was being heard within the context of Australian administrative law. Incidents such as this illustrate the risks of AI presenting erroneous information to unassuming individuals, and the harm this may cause within a legal context. This case in particular reinforced key insights I accrued while enrolled in ARTX3500, namely: the importance of precision when prompting LLMs, inherent biases held by LLMs, and the urgent need for regulated use of AI across the legal profession.

Insights taken from my legal experience and ARTX3500 have shaped my individual approach to AI integration in my educational and personal contexts. Drawing upon the Chief Justice of New South Wales' guidance on AI use in the legal profession, I continue to use LLMs primarily for clerical purposes such as scheduling and synthesising information. However, I remain wary of using LLMs to produce entire bodies of written work, given that I am aware of AI's biases and potential to produce misinformation.

Conclusive Remarks

I continue to maintain the view that LLMs should serve as assistive tools concomitant to the employment of independent critical thinking. This hypothesis is particularly apparent within the legal profession, where analytical reasoning is crucial to examining, applying and critiquing the law. While my understanding and appreciation of AI has evolved significantly over the course of the semester, I have found myself becoming increasingly strict as to how and when I use LLMs.

It is my view that human reasoning remains both necessary and inherent to the legal profession – a function that AI cannot replace or replicate. While LLMs can process and synthesise information efficiently, these technologies lack the capacity for contextual and ethical understanding. Due to this, I have therefore limited my use of LLMs to clerical and supporting functions as I do not wish for AI to reason for me. In doing so, I remain committed to ensuring that AI works alongside my own reasoning processes within a profession where precision, accountability and contextual nuance is crucial.

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